

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
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INFORMATION EXCHANGE AND CYBER DIPLOMACY THROUGH THE PARIS CALL: REACHING OUT HUMAN RIGHTS

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POLICY STATEMENT

The weakened control of the cyber domain by national institutions and international regimes represents an opportunity to circulate information and capital in an underhand manner, especially under emergencies like the Covid-19 pandemic. The circularity of information takes place intensively, while regulatory efforts take another step forward on the regulatory mechanisms of cyber interactions with the Paris Call initiative and corresponding working groups. But, though the incentives for a more intense economic fluidity with straightforward directives are under course, they cannot attend specifically human rights imbalances towards this scene.

Whereas we should recognize the effort to make this environment socially harmonious, the way out for a more efficient response involves resilience plans, and the use of interdependence counterbalances to guarantee compliance with regulations that can directly affect human rights. On one side, the spreading working groups mechanism used by the Paris Call after-Covid-19 pandemic may be a way to surpass limited Global North achievements considering the multistakeholder approach, but also, the aggregation of Global South institutions to uphold the commitment to areas and interdependent nexuses still not covered. On the other, the initiative still misses individual and collective human rights on dimensions that cross the efforts undertaken.

BACKGROUND

The acceleration of relationships in the global environment stems from technological advances and tech accessibility. Until the 1990s, the costs of obtaining stable channels for exchanging information in this environment kept away malicious organized or individual initiatives. Therefore, more accessible to spontaneous or organized frameworks around illicit flows, the cybernetic environment became more hostile and less trustful, although less costly. Initiatives are markedly spread and multi-sectorized, which was also a favorable condition to avoid the fostering of regulation [1].

However, an overlapping consensus emerges in the light of some of the efforts upheld by the Paris Forum to qualify some of the commitments around the future of specific governing values that surpass the cyber environment and can mark principles that reinforce regulatory mechanisms of more significant membership [2]. The Paris Call "for Trust and Security in Cyberspace" calls for all cyberspace actors to come together to face digital threats endangering citizens and infrastructure. Technology and peoples are at the same pace when considering the challenges that face institutions and individuals.

The next edition of the International Forum on Cybersecurity (FIC) will count on a Paris Call initiative focusing on three principles: protect the internet, defend intellectual property, and non-proliferation. Still, the human dimension is not covered to promote protection, so systems and policy frameworks are missing one crucial element: how people behind the technology will affect those at the ending point of the information channels, including artificial intelligence.

FINDINGS

The way policy development conditions compliance to regimes such as the Paris Call is critical. So, whereas states, people, and institutions will be able to look over to cyberinteraction in a predictable way is uncertain. The Carnegie Endowment for Peace [3] detects types of norms in course, which can be summarized as: those of multilateral cyber-diplomacy, those from private and industry stakeholders, and those derived from other collaborators such as think tanks, political parties, and NGOs. Thus, the unification of those efforts seems to be a prosperous project.

It should be noted that the Paris Call event as of September 2021 still remains on the institutional value of norms but rather the human value and scope of norms. It includes the way states and possible conflicting actors should contain cyber-arms proliferation [4], how they can avoid losses on intellectual property and how they could better protect the systems. But as cybersecurity is a social issue, it is not limited to cyber-infrastructure, and the cyber domain may also interact with the other ones. If cyber-resilience is also about capabilities to face threats, artificial intelligence may be of significant influence, while norms do not achieve this overlapping consensus on how people are responsible and may be affected by capabilities—last, who is to be punished and how to name actors in these frameworks. In the 1545th plenary meeting of the Conference on Disarmament, the citation of the Paris Call main objectives was rarely associated with the need of controlling the weaponization of the cyber domain and the Autonomous Weapons Systems challenges accordingly [5].

GDPR (into force in the EU since 2016) and equivalent regulations/legislations may be a paradigm-changing norm, but privacy is not the unique subject to be reflected [6]. The EU cyber-strategy, launched in December 2020 [7], marks the importance of partners' engagement in the same direction but cannot guarantee its bridging security to other domains than the infrastructure. Digital transformation is an umbrella that challenges those types of norms in some aspects: whether states can coordinate internal and external efforts to enhance cyber hygiene and security; if corporations are prepared to align with it; and if society is functional to participating in those processes observing and guaranteeing human rights on the various dimensions of the cyber domain.

CONCLUSIONS

Dr. Solange Ghernaoui [8] points that the Universal Declaration of Human Rights covers the subject clearly through its article 12: "No one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to attacks upon his honor and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks" [9]. Despite the organization of the Paris Call through UNESCO and the Paris Peace Forum, it still needs to be based on a broader view on the human attributes for a cyber-regulated domain, from the digital footprint rights of privacy to the human exposure to conditions of willful misconduct from third parties against her/his physical, mental or moral integrity. Therefore, risk assessment and enhancing cooperation to attend to critical threats to institutions do not comprehend people's protection under a common governance leadership.

The physical, mental or moral integrity of individuals should be a top political priority. Even if infrastructure development challenges states and corporations, there are two crossing dimensions that, once considered, could approximate policymakers to demands:

- 1) Cybercrime: against computers, through computers or on computers [10], considered the threats against individuals and institutions. This dimension includes cyber offenses and data misappropriation or attack.
- 2) Cyberwarfare: whether state or non-state operations, where artificial intelligence and/or systems permit reaching the target. Autonomous Weapons Systems (AWS) is part of the Cyberwarfare ambience; thus, International Humanitarian Law should govern it.

SUGGESTIONS

As proposed above, the dilemmas to be faced on regulatory schemes such as the Paris Call must include:

- 1) A Citizen Approach. As the beginner and end-user, people must be in the center of cyber-policies, which should include gravity on their rights and duties. Systems must be submitted to the citizen, not the opposite.
- 2) Inequality among actors. The different conditions of North and Global South stakeholders to adhere, including underdevelopment, but also, their different inefficiencies of controlling and compliance. Funding should also be considered, especially supporting the actors at the end of the pipe.
- 3) Cyberwarfare. The cyber domain is not a separate environment, and regulation should be thought through the understanding of its (a) ambiance of potential conflict and information warfare and (b) its ways to introduce and manipulate third parties infrastructure through artificial intelligence.
- 4) Attribution. A human-centered approach should consider attribution, especially to cyberweapons. As Barbieri et al. (2018) have stated, "Despite the above-mentioned difficulties in the application of IHL to cyber operations, some specific provisions could be implemented in cyberspace. IHL prohibits indiscriminate attacks, as well as indiscriminate means and methods of warfare. Thus, it constrains the use of any kind of weapon which is unable to distinguish between military and civilian targets". "Stop Killer Robots" campaign. "Fully autonomous weapons would lack the human judgment necessary to evaluate the proportionality of an attack (...); "It's unclear who, if anyone, could be held responsible for unlawful acts caused by a fully autonomous weapon."
<https://www.stopkillerrobots.org/>

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